
**BEST PRACTICES IN THE CHETANA'S SHRI. MANSUKHLAL
CHHAGANLAL LIBRARY**

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Abstract:

Libraries play a very important role in the 21st century. For, this is an era of information explosion. College library tries to provide maximum services provide to the users, that is, the students, staff, and external readers in a minimum cost. The global changes, particularly the Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) have impact on the functioning of academic libraries. Government of India, the UGC and the NAAC are seriously concerned with the task of improving standards of education and establishing best practices in the universities and colleges and their libraries. In the process if institutional accreditation, libraries play a crucial role. Library is the fulcrum of support for the entire range of academic activities on an educational campus. Libraries largely support learning, teaching and research process in institutions. The paper throws light on the best practices adopted by Chetana's Shri Mansukhlal Chhaganlal Library.

Keywords: Chetana College, Best Practices, NAAC, Library Services, Academic Libraries

Introduction:

The National Accreditation and Assessment Council (NAAC) strive for quality and excellence in higher education and advocates for enhancing the role of library and information services in improving academic environment. Document prepared by NAAC for Best practices in academic library say, "Best practices may be innovative and be a philosophy, policy, strategy, program, process or practice that solves a problem or create new opportunity and positively impact on organizations."

Meaning of 'Best Practices':

Best practices are defining by Jan Duffy as, 'Process that represent the most

effective way of achieving a specific objective' (Skyrme 2001)

Concise Oxford English Dictionary describes "Best practices as quality of most excellent or desirable type or most appropriate, advantageous, highly improved, outstanding, par excellence services or the customary or expected procedure or way of doing something that is usual or expected way in a particular organization or situation, guidelines for good practices. In this process of developing best practices we take action rather than good ideas, and we improve our skills" (Stevenson, & Waite, 2011)

ODLIS (Online Dictionary of Library and Information Science) describes best practices as follows: "In the

application of theory to real life situations, procedures that when properly applied consistently yield superior results and are therefore used as reference points in evaluation of the effectiveness of alternative methods of accomplishing the same task. Best practices are identified by examining empirical evidence of success.” (Reitz, 2015)

Thus a ‘Best practice’ in library in simple terms is known as that practice which makes the way for enhancing an existing function or an activity and helps in effective implementation or use of the process thereby leading to continuous improvement and overall performance of the library (NAAC,2006)

NAAC developed a set of best practices followed in academic libraries and presented under the following four broad areas:

1. Management and Administration of a Library:

- In-service Programme.
- Observation of other Library practice.
- Staff promotional policy.
- Maintenance of service area.
- Special deposit scheme.
- Resource generation through external membership.
- Resource generation through internal services.
- Student participation programme.

2. Collection and Services:

- Collection development in different formats.
- Compact storage of less used collection.
- Library book exhibition.
- Extended library opening hours.
- Extended hours of service.

3. Extent of use of services:

- User education initiation of new users.

- Preparatory course for student’s project.
- User orientation information aids.
- Library use statistics.
- Library best user award.
- User feedback practice through different formats.
- Suggestion box and timely response.

4. Use of Technology in Libraries:

- On-line information retrieval - Internet access.
- Free browsing unit – Internet access.
- Broadband internet Centre.
- Library homepage for information dissemination.
- A strong and dynamic library website.
- User feedback through library homepage.
- Access to e-resources.
- Information retrieval through web OPAC.
- Campus – wide LAN facility.
- Database creation using international standard formats.
- Electronic surveillance system CCTV.

For college library NAAC has developed the following set of best practices for college libraries:

1. Computerization of library with standard software.
2. Inclusion of sufficient information about the library in college prospectus.
3. Compiling student / teacher statistics.
4. Displaying newspaper clippings and clipping file maintained periodically.
5. Career / employment information services.
6. Internet facility to different user groups.
7. Information literacy programmes.

8. Suggestion Box.
9. Displaying New Arrivals.
10. Conduct book exhibition on different occasions.
11. Organizing book talks.
12. Instituting Annual Best Use Award for Students.
13. Organizing competitions annually.
14. Conduct user survey periodically.

About Shri Mansukhlal Chhaganlal Library:

The Library of CHETANA'S Hazarimal Somani College of Commerce & Economics, Smt. Kusumtai Chaudhari College of Arts, was established in 1970 along with the college by former Education Minister Shri Madhukar Chaudhari. The aim of the college is to provide education to lower strata of the society. The library is situated on the ground floor of the college building. At present it has a rich collection of 112142 books, 548 bound volumes and 592 CDs/Video. Having established a user-friendly environment in the library the librarian along with other professionals and Semi professionals are managing the library with proficiency & effective library services. Library is fully computerized with SLIM21 Library Software. All the work of the library is done with help of this software.

It also provides Internet facility to Teachers and Students and has a book-bank facility for the needy and deserving students. Last two-year book-bank service was provided to junior college students also. Beside this it has services like references, circulars, bibliographies; inter library loan facility, current awareness etc. Library staff conducts the library orientation program for fresher to make them aware of library facilities and services. It arranges special books' exhibitions on different occasion. Our

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library also provides open access to all our Students.

Vision and Mission of the Library:

Vision:

- To make our students develop knowledge as power to become competent and self-reliant through information.

Mission:

- User satisfaction through timely and quality service
- To facilitate our readers with modern technology and more numbers of the resources in the library.
- To motivate reading habits among our readers by maximum utilization of library resources.

Best Practices of Chetana's Mansukhlal Chhaganlal Library:

1. Library Committee:

Chetana's College Library formed library committee to formulate policies and guidelines for the smooth functioning of library activities. The committee mainly finalized the library budget for the Academic Year, administers the overall functioning of the library, discuss issues related to the new services to be introduced, purchase of equipment required for the library, any staff issues and user's suggestions.

Objective of LAC:

- Advise the Librarian regarding proposed policies.
- Define the policy about development and administration of the Library. Express the opinions of the faculty, staff and students.
- To understand the need of library. Make general Library policy.
- Sanctioning the budget.
- Develop the process for procurement of Journal & E-Books.

Significant initiatives of LAC:

- Framed collection development policies.
- Subscription of Periodicals.
- Collection Development in subjects.
- Distribution of Set of Books for needy students
- Exhibition of books for enriching collection

Orientation Programme:

To create awareness amongst the users about the existing facilities, services provided by the library. Every year library organizes this types of programme to fresher. During this programme library provided detail information about the services and facility available in library to optimum utilization the same.

Objective:

- Creating awareness on library resources, facilities and services among new user and thus to ensure optimum use.
- To develop reading habit among the students.
- Friendly approach towards the library. So, students are attracted towards the library, they feel free to tell their problems to the librarian.

Book Bank Scheme:

Our college library has been participating in Book Bank Scheme for Reserved Category students. Funds are received from University of Mumbai. The 'Book Bank Scheme' for the needy and deserving students of all classes. Every academic year library provides book bank facility for SC, ST and NT cast students. Library also having book bank facility to open category students against taken refundable amount of Rs.200/-.

Objective & Benefit of the Book Bank Facility:

- To provide books for the full academic year to the students as per availability of books.
- To support the students to increase their reading habits.
- The needy and clever students get set of books for the whole academic year.
- The circulation load on the library staff is relieved by this scheme.
- A large number of students are benefitted by and are being benefitted by this scheme.

Last five years' usages record of Book Bank Scheme:

Sr. No	Academic Year	Beneficiary Users		Total
		Open Book Bank	Reserved Book Bank	
1	2018 - 2019	57	55	112
2	2019 - 2020	106	80	186
3	2020 - 2021	96	90	186
4	2021 - 2022	98	90	188
5	2022 - 2023	110	117	227

Library Book Exhibition:

College Library arrange book exhibition on different occasions like national leaders Jayanti such as Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar, Mahatma Gandhi, Vachan Prerana Devas etc. an exhibition of books on these personalities is displayed. Library display rare books, newly added books or books of particular subject which are available in the library. This will lead to increased awareness among readers about knowledge wealth

the library possess they can demand the books accordingly.

Library also arrange annual book exhibition to various publisher and distributor are called for the exhibition.

Objective:

- To goal is to spread awareness among the students on the latest print and existing books available in their subjects.
- To increase the awareness of the students about the collection of library on various topics and themes.

Library Automation:

College Library is fully automated with SLIM21 library software. All the work of the library done with the help of software. The books are bar- coded and students and teacher having bar- code library card. Library having one Bar-code machine and 6 bar-code scanner for the book circulation.

Objective:

- To get accreditation from NAAC and to ease the library staff in their day to day functions.
- It improved the quality of services, increased productivity and easily maintained library statistics.

Best Library User Award:

To promote the cultivate good reading habits among students and staff library has instituted best user awards. Best user award is constituted to the students who read maximum books for the academic year. The data is gathered through the software maintained by the library staff. Usage data is compiled through circulation of library items. Base on the above data and observation of the librarian best user awards are given to the user who has made maximum use of the

library. Certificate and prize are given to the best library user.

Objective:

- To attract more users to visit the library and use the resources.
- To increase to use of library reference materials, literatures and other resources.

New Paper Clipping and Career Oriented Innovative Board:

Important articles related to Education, Library Science, Great Personality, New about the college etc. are cut from the newspapers and make separate file for store. Library also cut career oriented advertise, news and display on notice board like MPSC, UPSC, BANK Exam, and other government exam info etc.

Objective:

- To create awareness among the readers about competitive exam, well known personality.
- To provide information about current affairs to students.
- To keep up to date knowledge to students.

Display of New Arrival:

Newly processed books are regularly displayed on New Arrival display rack and same list are put on the Student and staff room notice board. This is to inform the readers about newly added books in the library collections.

Objective:

- To attract more users to visit the library and use the resources.
- User know the new books and more curious, excitement to read.

Library Statistical Charts:

Library statistics data are capture with the help of SLIM21 and also register and maintained for all services given and

paper chart has been put on the notice board.

Objective:

- To gather data on the use of facilities and services.
- To enable to assess and increase the quality of services delivered by the library.
- To know more about day to day work of the library.

Provision of E-Books & E-Journals:

The library has a membership of UGC INFLIBNET NLIST program through which each user can access more than 6000 e-journals and 799500 e-books free of cost. Each user having individual login id.

Objective:

- To help teacher to up to date knowledge in their subject through online resources.
- To help students for their educational development & research activities work.

Social Responsibility:

As a social responsibility college library given the reading membership to outside students, those who are doing CA, LAW, NET/SET, MPSC, UPSC and other competitive examination study. College also having member of Marathi literature person nearby government colony.

Objective:

- As we provide library facilities without any charges to neighboring students.
- Ex-Students make use of our facilities for prepare competitive exams.

Library Portal:

College Library developed library portal chetanalibrary.webs.com. A portal is a single user interface for accessing wide

variety of electronic resources both within and outside the library. The portal technology has enabled librarians to shift to a more proactive, user-centered and service oriented model of library. Library portal is the website, providing access to all relevant e-resources at one point.

Objective:

- Library Portal enable the user to familiarize with the library activities and services through the remote access.

OPAC & WEB OPAC(Online Public Access Catalogue):

The Online Public Access Catalogue is an important tool for searching the exact source of information preserved and organized in the library. Various options are provided to search the book like Title, Author, Publisher, Accession Number, Keywords etc. Users find it very convenient and time saving to locate the book.

Objective:

- Users find it very convenient and time saving to locate the book.
- Training programmes should be conduct for student, teacher every year for two to three days as per their need. In this programme, how to find out library books by using Library OPAC & Web OPAC has been given.

Library Help Desk:

The Library has developed library help desk where all the library related document such as library Information Brochure, Membership form, Demand slip, Feedback form, Book Requisition form, Suggestion form are made available to save the time of staff and library users.

Objective:

- To save the time of user and staff.

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